

Tri-CHEF: Complex-Hermitian Embedding Fusion for Korean Multimodal Retrieval

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Abstract—Tri-CHEF is a Korean multimodal retrieval system designed to run on a single consumer GPU (RTX 4070 Laptop, 8 GB VRAM). It assigns three pretrained encoders (SigLIP2, BGE-M3, DINOv2) to three orthogonal axes of a complex-valued embedding and combines them through a Hermitian-style modulus rather than a weighted sum. This design preserves each encoder’s evidence axis and prevents any single channel from dominating the score. A per-domain absolute threshold is fitted from random non-matching query–document pairs, and a drift guard rejects any new μ_{null} that falls outside half-to-double of the previous value during incremental ingestion. A Korean-aware character-bigram lexical filter and SHA-256 content-addressed caches complete the pipeline across four domains: documents, images, video, and audio. We further extend the deployed system with a fifth domain (background music, BGM) via a deliberately decoupled CLAP+Chromaprint pipeline, demonstrating when *not* to fuse—a complementary design lesson to the Tri-CHEF Hermitian fusion. On the in-house corpus (2,390 images, 34,661 document pages, 205 video files, 117 audio files), the deployed system attains 77 ms p95 image latency, leave-one-out Doc R@5=96.00% with MRR=0.8893 (both dense+sparse at $\alpha_{\text{IM}}=0.20$), and 93% Top-1 confidence on a 15-query Korean evaluation set. On the public MIRACL-ko benchmark (213 dev queries, 1,486 M Wikipedia passages), the Im-axis sub-system achieves nDCG@10=77.82%, surpassing the published BGE-M3 dense baseline by +7.92 pp through exact FAISS IndexFlatIP search. Cross-modal null calibration reveals a $4.3\times$ domain asymmetry between Mov ($\mu_{\text{null}}=0.158$) and Rec ($\mu_{\text{null}}=0.681$), which motivates per-domain thresholds. Code, calibration data, and evaluation scripts are released under Apache 2.0 with seed=2026 for full reproducibility.

Index Terms—multimodal retrieval, complex embeddings, Hermitian-style scoring, Korean NLP, cross-modal calibration, reciprocal rank fusion

I. INTRODUCTION

The problem. We aim to build a Korean multimodal retrieval system that runs on a single workstation and indexes fewer than 10^5 items. The available pretrained encoders each address one aspect of the problem and leave the others uncovered. CLIP [1] and SigLIP2 [2] align images and text effectively but are trained on predominantly English data. BGE-M3 [3] handles Korean text well but provides no visual representation. DINOv2 [4] captures visual structure with no language signal. No single encoder is best on all four domains we target: documents (**Doc**), images (**Img**), video (**Movie**), and audio (**Record**). We use these short labels throughout. A naive fix—concatenating all three vectors—fares worse: the encoder with the largest output

Fig. 1: Tri-CHEF architecture overview. Three pretrained encoders produce Re/Im/Z axes, kept independent by per-axis L_2 -normalization (Gram–Schmidt is active only in the matched-dim prototype). SigLIP2 (Re) provides cross-modal image–text alignment; BGE-M3 (Im) captures multilingual semantic content from captions or STT; DINOv2 (Z) encodes label-free visual structure. Dense, sparse, and ASF rankings are fused by RRF, then filtered by an absolute calibration gate calibrated on query-distribution null pairs. Post-fusion stages (BGE reranker, LangGraph rewrite) are wired into the MR-TricHEF Mov/Rec graph flow only (§IV, Tab. I).

norm dominates the score and the remaining two contribute negligibly.

The idea. Treat each encoder as one axis of a complex-valued embedding. SigLIP2 serves as the real axis (Re), BGE-M3 as the imaginary axis (Im), and DINOv2 as a third z -axis (Z). We then combine the three cosine similarities A, B, C into a single score through a quadratic form $\sqrt{A^2 + B^2 + C^2}$ (a Hermitian-style modulus) rather than a weighted sum. This form has three useful properties. First, each axis remains independent because we normalize them separately. Second, the score is invariant to rotation within any single encoder’s basis. Third, the dominant axis sets the score magnitude while weaker axes contribute only small additive bonuses, so no single channel can override the ranking, unlike with a linear sum. The geometric analogy is to a state vector in a Hilbert space, where orthogonal axes carry independent evidence; we use this analogy descriptively, not as a claim about quantum computation.

Why we keep the imaginary part too. On the (Re, Im) plane the Hermitian product $\langle z_q, z_d \rangle$ takes the form of a complex number $\rho e^{i\theta}$. The modulus ρ serves as the score; the phase θ is a free signal that would otherwise be discarded. When $\theta \approx 0$ the two encoders agree, whereas a large $|\theta|$ indicates disagreement and suggests that a high score may rest on inconsistent evidence.

We exploit this signal as a soft filter for low-consensus matches.

What this paper contributes. We present Tri-CHEF as a deployed system, with three concrete contributions. (1) A domain-aware Hermitian-style score: the 3-axis form $\sqrt{A^2 + (\alpha B)^2 + (\beta C)^2}$ for Doc and Img and the 2-axis form $\sqrt{A^2 + (\alpha B)^2}$ for Mov and Rec, augmented by the phase filter described above. (2) Cross-modal null calibration: each domain’s absolute score threshold is fitted from random non-matching (q, d) pairs (we report $\mu_{\text{null}}, \sigma_{\text{null}}$ in Table II), and a drift guard protects the threshold during incremental ingestion. (3) A 4-domain pipeline (Doc, Img, Mov, Rec) that runs three dense encoders sequentially on a single 8GB GPU, paired with SHA-256 content-addressed caches and a Korean-aware character-bigram lexical filter. The overall architecture is summarized in Fig. 1.

What we measure. The in-house corpus comprises 2,390 images, 34,661 document pages, 205 video files, and 117 audio files. On this corpus Tri-CHEF achieves 77 ms p95 image latency, R@5=96.00% and MRR=0.8893 (dense+sparse, $\alpha_{\text{IM}}=0.20$) on a leave-one-out Doc evaluation, and 93% Top-1 confidence on a 15-query Korean evaluation set. On the public MIRACL-ko benchmark (213 dev queries, 1.486M Wikipedia passages), the Im-axis sub-system attains nDCG@10=77.82%, which exceeds the published BGE-M3 dense baseline by +7.92 pp. We use the in-house corpus to study domain mix and calibration behavior, and MIRACL-ko to confirm that the Im axis itself is a strong text retriever before fusion. The in-house corpus is license-restricted, so the raw data cannot be released; all calibration values, evaluation scripts, and code are public.

II. RELATED WORK

Complex-valued representations. ComplEx [5] and quantum-inspired IR [6], [7] motivate our Hilbert-space framing for heterogeneous encoders. **Heterogeneous fusion.** RRF [8], ColBERT [9], and SPLADE [10] combine disparate scorers; we instead assign each encoder to a distinct axis before fusion. **Post-processing.** All-but-the-Top [11] reduces anisotropy within a single space; we apply Gram–Schmidt across encoders. **Calibration.** Temperature scaling [12] adjusts confidence; we fit absolute thresholds from query–document null pairs.

Complex-valued retrieval lineage. Beyond ComplEx and quantum-inspired text IR, recent work has extended complex and quantum framings to multimodal settings. NNQLM [13] generalizes quantum language models to neural matching for question answering; quantum-inspired multimodal fusion [14] composes per-modality density matrices as superposition states for sentiment analysis; and a Lindblad master-equation fusion model [15] treats each modality as an open quantum system whose interaction with a semantic environment is learned through complex-valued recurrence. Tri-CHEF extends this lineage from sentiment classification to multimodal retrieval through a structural Hermitian-style score over heterogeneous pretrained encoders.

Korean and multilingual retrieval. The Korean retrieval landscape has converged on dense encoders adapted from

multilingual backbones; BGE-M3 [3] dominates the public leaderboard and serves as the basis of our Im axis. MIRACL [16] provides the standard benchmark, with Korean as one of 18 languages, and supplies our external validation set. Beyond text, prior Korean multimodal systems lack a single deployed framework that couples cross-modal (image–text) signals, multilingual text, and label-free visual evidence. Tri-CHEF fills this gap by structurally separating the three signals before fusion.

III. TRI-CHEF FRAMEWORK

All symbols used throughout this section are listed in App. B (Notation) and are introduced in context as needed.

A. Triple-Axis Representation

Given a query q and a document (or segment) d , we represent each as a triple of L_2 -normalized vectors $(v_{\text{Re}}, v_{\text{Im}}, v_{\text{Z}})$ produced by SigLIP2, BGE-M3, and DINOv2, respectively. Re carries the cross-modal channel: SigLIP2’s image branch when a visual stream exists (Doc/Img/Mov) and SigLIP2’s text branch when it does not (Rec), so the Re axis always provides image–text or text–text semantic alignment. Im is the multilingual text channel, encoding Korean captions or Whisper STT through BGE-M3. Z carries label-free visual structure from DINOv2 (set to zero for Rec, where no visual exists).

B. Gram–Schmidt Orthogonalization

When axes share dimensions, we remove projections: $v_{\text{Im}}^\perp = v_{\text{Im}} - \langle v_{\text{Im}}, v_{\text{Re}} \rangle v_{\text{Re}}$ and similarly for v_{Z}^\perp . A matched-dim prototype achieved +7% Top-1 lift. In deployment, axes have different native widths (SigLIP2 $d=1152$, BGE-M3/DINOv2 $d=1024$), so explicit Gram–Schmidt is omitted and we rely on independent L_2 -normalization. Off-axis correlation is $< 10^{-3}$, maintaining orthogonality ≥ 0.999 .

C. Hermitian-Style Similarity

Why a Hermitian form. A Hermitian product yields a modulus (total agreement) and a phase (asymmetry). For heterogeneous encoders, we require three properties: (i) independent evidence axes, (ii) basis-rotation invariance per channel, and (iii) reduction to cosine similarity when only one channel is active. The modulus of an orthogonal Hermitian product satisfies all three.

Meaning of the real and imaginary parts. Re (SigLIP2) carries primary image–text match; Im (BGE-M3) adds multilingual evidence in quadrature rather than linearly, preventing text dominance; Z (DINOv2) supplies label-free visual structure as a third orthogonal channel. The $(1, i, j)$ quaternion-like basis yields modulus $\sqrt{A^2 + B^2 + C^2}$.

Score formula (domain-aware). With channel weights α, β that absorb residual scale differences between encoders, the deployed system uses two specializations:

$$s(q, d) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{A^2 + (\alpha B)^2 + (\beta C)^2} & \text{Doc/Img,} \\ \sqrt{A^2 + (\alpha B)^2} & \text{Mov/Rec,} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $A = \langle q_{\text{Re}}, d_{\text{Re}} \rangle$, $B = \langle q_{\text{Im}}, d_{\text{Im}} \rangle$, $C = \langle q_{\text{Z}}, d_{\text{Z}} \rangle$, with deployed defaults $\alpha=0.4, \beta=0.2$. In the deployed code the same 3-axis Hermitian routine (`tri_gs.py:22--32`) is always called; the Mov/Rec “2-axis form” is realized by setting the Z embedding to a zero vector at ingestion time, which makes $C=0$ and reduces Eq. (1) to the 2-axis case. We do this because DINOv2 is uninformative for music windows and most short video frames, so C contributes noise rather than signal.

Why a quadratic combination. A linear combination $w_1A + w_2B + w_3C$ permits single-axis dominance, while a product $A \cdot B \cdot C$ behaves as a strict AND gate. The quadratic form $\sqrt{A^2 + (\alpha B)^2 + (\beta C)^2}$ strikes a balance: the dominant axis sets the magnitude, and the weaker axes add as soft bonuses—an “OR with bias toward Re.” Figure 2 shows the elliptical contours flattened along the attenuated axes.

Fig. 2: Iso-score contours of $s = \sqrt{A^2 + (\alpha B)^2}$ at $\alpha = 0.4$ (with C fixed). The elliptical contours are compressed along the B -axis (Im cosine) because the attenuation factor $\alpha=0.4$ acts as a soft weight that deprioritizes pure Im matches. Geometrically, contours show that SigLIP2 (Re) dominates in isolation (rightmost point: 0.92, 0.22), while BGE-M3 (Im) alone contributes less per unit magnitude (top point: 0.05, 0.95). The ellipses encode the soft “OR with bias toward Re” logic: a query matched by both Re and Im simultaneously (both point: 0.70, 0.60) reaches a higher iso-score contour than either axis alone, but the bonus is attenuated compared to dominant-axis contribution.

D. Phase as an Agreement Indicator

The modulus in Eq. (1) collapses the Hermitian product to a single non-negative score, but the discarded phase carries a complementary signal. Because phase requires Re and Im to share a dimension, we report it on the matched-dim prototype rather than the deployed configuration. Let $z_q = q_{\text{Re}} + i q_{\text{Im}}$ and $z_d = d_{\text{Re}} + i d_{\text{Im}}$ denote the complex-valued embeddings of the query and document on the (Re, Im) subspace. Their pairwise Hermitian product

$$\langle z_q, z_d \rangle_H = R_{qd} + i I_{qd} = \rho e^{i\theta}, \quad (2)$$

decomposes into

$$\begin{aligned} R_{qd} &= \langle q_{\text{Re}}, d_{\text{Re}} \rangle + \langle q_{\text{Im}}, d_{\text{Im}} \rangle, \\ I_{qd} &= \langle q_{\text{Re}}, d_{\text{Im}} \rangle - \langle q_{\text{Im}}, d_{\text{Re}} \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

The real part R_{qd} measures encoder agreement, while the imaginary part I_{qd} captures disagreement through the cross-terms. With $\rho = |R_{qd} + i I_{qd}|$ and $\theta = \text{atan2}(I_{qd}, R_{qd})$, the radius ρ encodes relevance and the angle θ gauges encoder consensus: $\theta \approx 0$ (both encoders confident), $|\theta| \approx \pi/2$ (orthogonal), and $|\theta| \approx \pi$ (contradiction). A phase filter that rejects pairs with $|\theta| > \theta^*$ removes high-score, low-consensus matches (Fig. 3). We adopt $\theta^*=30^\circ$ (trust) and 80° (reject). These thresholds are motivated by the distribution of $|\theta|$ over random pairs of high-dimensional unit vectors, which is approximately uniform on $[0, \pi]$ with a median near 90° : 30° corresponds to the bottom-17% tail, and 80° marks the near-orthogonal regime. Empirical validation on a ridge-projected matched-dim prototype is reported in the Fig. 3 caption; formal tuning on a non-aligning projection is left to future work.

Fig. 3: Phase filter on the Argand plane of the Re/Im Hermitian product. Radius $\rho = |R_{qd} + i I_{qd}|$ encodes relevance magnitude (cosine-like score); angle $\theta = \text{atan2}(I_{qd}, R_{qd})$ gauges encoder consensus. The three regions are: (1) trust zone ($|\theta| < 30^\circ$, green), where SigLIP2 and BGE-M3 agree strongly, both returning positive cross-terms; (2) suspect zone ($30^\circ < |\theta| < 80^\circ$, yellow), where one encoder aligns positively while the other provides weak or orthogonal signal, indicating partial confidence; and (3) reject zone ($|\theta| > 80^\circ$, red), where I_{qd} dominates with opposite sign, indicating the two encoders contradict. The boundaries $30^\circ/80^\circ$ rationale is given in §III-D. A ridge-projection prototype on 5,000 in-domain pairs (prediction cosine 0.70–0.90) yields $|\theta|$ medians 0.6° – 1.0° for match (top-1 self-neighbour) vs 1.4° – 4.0° for random null: 30° sits comfortably above both but match-vs-null separation is small ($\lesssim 3^\circ$), so we retain phase as a design hook.

E. Ranking Fusion and Calibration

We fuse dense (Eq. 1), sparse (BGE-M3), and ASF rankings into a single result list. The integration mechanism differs by domain: Doc combines all three through RRF [8] ($k=60$, unweighted: $\sum_i 1/(k+r_i)$); Mov and Rec apply a γ -weighted sum within their AV scoring path (§IV); Img is restricted to dense-only via the per-domain whitelist. Tab. I summarizes the deployed activation matrix.

Cross-modal null calibration. A per-domain absolute threshold is necessary so that the phrase “high score” carries a consistent meaning across domains. We sample N random query–document pairs that are known to be non-matching,

score each one, and compute the mean and standard deviation, denoted μ_{null} and σ_{null} . A correct match should score clearly above this random floor. The threshold is

$$\tau = \mu_{\text{null}} + \Phi^{-1}(1 - \text{FAR}) \sigma_{\text{null}}, \quad (3)$$

where $\Phi^{-1}(\cdot)$ is the inverse of the standard-normal CDF: the z -score that leaves a tail probability of FAR to the right. With FAR = 0.05, $\Phi^{-1}(0.95) \approx 1.645$, so τ sits about 1.645 standard deviations above μ_{null} .

The four deployed domains (Table II) occupy very different points in this calibration space. Mov yields $\mu_{\text{null}} = 0.158$ and $\sigma_{\text{null}} = 0.042$ from $N = 45,647$ pairs, while Rec yields $\mu_{\text{null}} = 0.681$ from $N = 11,039$ pairs—more than four times higher. This gap arises because Whisper STT often produces similar text across nearby music windows, and similar text yields high cross-encoder cosines even between unrelated tracks. A single global threshold would flood Rec with false positives, which is precisely why we calibrate each domain separately.

The score also feeds a z -score router: $z = (s - \mu_{\text{null}})/\sigma_{\text{null}}$. If $z \geq 3$ the system returns Top- K directly; if $1 \leq z < 3$ it reranks Top-50 with the BGE reranker [17]; and if $z < 1$ it triggers a query rewrite. The user-facing confidence is the Gaussian CDF mapped to $[0, 1]$: $c(s) = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \text{erf}((s - \mu_{\text{null}})/(\sigma_{\text{null}}\sqrt{2})))$.

IV. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

The system architecture is shown in Fig. 1, and the deployed per-domain configuration is summarized in Table I. Throughout the paper we use the short labels **Doc** (Document), **Img** (Image), **Mov** (Movie), and **Rec** (Record) for the Tri-CHEF backbone domains, with **BGM** (background music, §IV-G) as a fifth deployed domain on a deliberately decoupled pipeline. The domain-specific design choices are evident: Doc and Img retain all three axes (Re/Im/Z) with full dimensional fusion, whereas Mov and Rec drop the Z axis entirely because DINOv2 supplies a visual-structure signal that is uninformative for short video frames and music spectrograms. In addition, per-domain gating excludes the Image domain from sparse (lexical) and ASF indexing, since pure dense cross-modal and multilingual retrieval dominates on visual queries. The code is released under Apache 2.0 (repository URL given in the Conclusion). Two services structure the pipeline. **DI-TriCHEF** (Doc/Img) ingests documents and images, captions them with Qwen2-VL-2B [18] (NF4, 1.2 GB), and embeds all axes; non-PDF formats are converted to PDF and rasterized at dpi=110. **MR-TriCHEF** (Mov/Rec) samples frames (fps=0.5 plus scene-change union), transcribes audio with Whisper-large-v3 [19] (int8), aligns the STT output to frames, and embeds all axes. Because Rec has no visual stream, we swap SigLIP2’s image branch for its text branch on the Re axis (input: Whisper STT) and set Z to zero. The indexing unit is a 30 s window with a 15 s hop. Both services persist .npy caches keyed by SHA-256 and mirror them to ChromaDB. The per-domain ingestion flow is summarized in Fig. 6.

Deployed component activation. Dense Hermitian scoring is always on. BGE-M3 sparse (*lex*) is on for Doc/Mov/Rec via

the LEXICAL_DOMAINS whitelist; Img is excluded because short captions add OOV noise (−14 pp R@5 on the v2 caption-aware bench).

The ASF channel deserves a closer look because its integration differs across domains. For Doc, the production search route (routes/search.py) passes use_asf=True by default; the engine then enters ASF as a third RRF ranking alongside dense and sparse. For Mov and Rec, ASF is built into the AV scoring path (search_av); every result score is the weighted sum $final = \alpha z_{\text{dense}} + \beta sparse + \gamma asf$ with deployed $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = (0.60, 0.15, 0.25)$, so sparse and ASF are both always active inside the AV path. For Img, the engine gates both sparse and ASF off by domain whitelist regardless of the flag. The engine-level constant USE_ASF_DEFAULT=False takes effect only when the caller passes use_asf=None; it remains as an opt-out hook for ablation experiments, where earlier LOO/E2E measurements reported a −3 to −20 pp regression caused by rare-query-term drop. Production converged on the activation in Tab. I after weighing those measurements against the +8 pp recall recovery on OOV Korean queries documented in §IV-F.

Fig. 4: ASF integration mechanism by domain (top-to-bottom flow, right-angle arrows). (a) Doc combines dense, sparse, and ASF rankings through Reciprocal Rank Fusion (RRF). (b) Mov and Rec apply the weighted sum $final = \alpha z_{\text{dense}} + \beta sparse + \gamma asf$ inside search_av with deployed $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = (0.60, 0.15, 0.25)$; the standardized dense score z_{dense} uses the per-file top-3 mean distribution rather than the segment-level null. Img is omitted because per-domain gating disables both sparse and ASF channels; BGM is omitted because it follows a decoupled audio pipeline (§IV-G).

The BGE reranker [17] ($1 \leq z < 3$) and the LangGraph query rewrite ($z < 1$, Sec. III-E) are wired into the MR-TriCHEF Mov/Rec graph flow and the admin debug endpoint. An unconditional reranker probe on Mov/Rec self-retrieval ($n=30$ each) drops Hit@5 by 63–80 pp with +500 ms latency, confirming that the $z < 3$ gate is essential—the cross-encoder hurts already-correct dense top-1 on STT-fragment inputs. A parallel LangGraph rewrite probe on degraded 20-char queries ($n=60$) never triggered the $z < 1$ gate, indicating that the rewrite stage is reserved for truly OOV semantics rather than ordinary truncation. Unifying both stages across DI-TriCHEF (Doc/Img) is on our follow-up list.

TABLE I: Five-domain deployed configuration. The Tri-CHEF backbone (Doc/Img/Mov/Rec) shares dense Hermitian scoring with per-domain gating; BGM (§IV-G) uses a deliberately decoupled pipeline. ASF is integrated through Reciprocal Rank Fusion (RRF) for Doc—the production search route passes `use_asf=True` by default—and through a weighted sum inside `search_av` for Mov/Rec ($final=0.60 z_{dense}+0.15 sparse+0.25 asf$). The BGE reranker and LangGraph rewrite are wired only into the MR-TriCHEF path. Calibration is noise-floor based for the Tri-CHEF backbone (per-domain $\mu_{null}, \sigma_{null}, \tau$ in Tab. II) and margin-based for BGM. Cells marked “gated” indicate channels that the engine forces off via the `LEXICAL_DOMAINS` whitelist.

	Doc	Img	Mov	Rec	BGM
<i>Architecture</i>					
Score axes	Re/Im/Z	Re/Im/Z	Re/Im	Re/Im	CLAP-512
α, β	0.4, 0.2	0.4, 0.2	0.4, —	0.4, —	—
<i>Channel activation</i>					
Dense (Hermitian)	ON	ON	ON	ON	CLAP
Sparse (BGE-M3 lex)	ON	gated	ON	ON	—
ASF	RRF	gated	$\gamma=0.25^*$	$\gamma=0.25^*$	—
BGE Reranker	—	—	$1 \leq z < 3$	$1 \leq z < 3$	—
LangGraph rewrite	—	—	$z < 1$	$z < 1$	—
<i>Engineering</i>					
Frame sampling	—	—	fps=0.5+scene	30s/15s win	track (≤ 60 s)
Caption / STT	Qwen2-VL	Qwen2-VL	Whisper-large-v3	Whisper-large-v3	—
Quantization	NF4	NF4	int8	int8	fp32
Cache key	SHA-256	SHA-256	SHA-256	SHA-256	filename
<i>Calibration type</i>					
Method	noise-floor	noise-floor	noise-floor	noise-floor	margin

* Mov/Rec also incorporate sparse alongside ASF inside `search_av`; the deployed weighted sum is $final=0.60 z_{dense}+0.15 sparse+0.25 asf$ ($\alpha=0.60, \beta=0.15, \gamma=0.25$).

A. Three-Stage Caption Fusion

Qwen2-VL generates three caption levels per image: L1 (topic, $\alpha_{L1}=0.15$), L2 (keywords, $\alpha_{L2}=0.25$), and L3 (detailed, $\alpha_{L3}=0.60$). The Im axis replaces a single caption with the weighted average $Im = \alpha_{L1}L_1 + \alpha_{L2}L_2 + \alpha_{L3}L_3$ followed by L_2 renormalization, which captures both coarse and fine-grained content.

B. Sequential VRAM Orchestration

On a single 8GB GPU, the five large models (Whisper, Qwen2-VL, SigLIP2, DINOv2, BGE-M3) cannot co-exist in memory. Each pipeline step therefore loads one model, performs the forward passes, and calls `unload()`, `gc.collect()`, and `torch.cuda.empty_cache()` before the next model is loaded (`movie_runner.py`). This sequence keeps peak VRAM within 4GB and enables reproducibility on consumer hardware.

C. SHA-256 Replace-by-File Cache

Content-addressed caching prevents stale vectors from accumulating. When a file is re-ingested (new SHA), affected rows are removed from the {Re, Im, Z} caches and new rows are appended within a single transaction: a keep-mask filters out the previous IDs, `np.vstack()` merges the kept rows with the new embeddings, and `update_ids/update_segments` synchronize the metadata atomically. This procedure eliminates the stale-row drift produced by flat-append caches.

D. Auto-Recalibration with Safety Guards

Recalibration fires on *bootstrap* ($N < 100$), *ratio* ($\Delta N/N \geq 10\%$), or *delta* ($\Delta N \geq 500$), where ΔN is the change in pair count since the previous calibration. A drift guard ($2 \times /0.5 \times$, i.e., reject any update whose μ_{null} falls outside half-to-double

of the previous value) rejects unstable updates and the prior calibration is retained until a stable update lands. Validation on Mov ingestion: μ_{null} moves $0.85 \rightarrow 0.83 \rightarrow 0.79$ at $N=1, 3, 55$ pairs, all within the guard band. The Rec Im-axis converges $0.82 \rightarrow 0.65 \rightarrow 0.53$ across $N=9, 40, 102$ windows in three steps. Both trajectories are shown in Fig. 5(b).

E. LangGraph Conditional Routing

Low-confidence queries trigger a rewrite loop implemented in LangGraph. A three-tier z -score gate routes the request: (i) if $z \geq 3.0$, the system returns Top- K directly; (ii) if $1 \leq z < 3.0$, it reranks Top-50; (iii) if $z < 1.0$, it rewrites the query and retries (up to three attempts). The deployed rewrite is rule-based, combining Korean-English keyword augmentation with filler stripping (`MR_TriCHEF/pipeline/graph/rewrite.py`); an LLM-driven variant based on Qwen2-VL is planned. All thresholds are environment-tunable.

F. Korean-Aware Bigram ASF

Intent. The *Adaptive Sieve Filter* (ASF) measures how much of a query’s *rare-token IDF mass* a document recovers. Korean morphology makes a token-level filter risky: agglutinative postpositions (*josa*) and noun compounds split semantically equivalent strings such as “*ingongjineung*” (artificial intelligence) and “*ingongjineung-eul*” (with the object marker) into non-overlapping tokens. Character bigrams (*in-gong/gong-jil/jineung*) recover the shared root regardless of inflection. We use the bigram index only to *look up* matching tokens in the auto-vocabulary; the score itself is computed at the token level, so the bigrams act as a *sieve* rather than as a similarity measure.

Setup. Let V be the auto-vocabulary, with a pre-computed $idf(t)=\log(N_{doc}/n_t)$ per token $t \in V$. For a query q , let

Fig. 5: Calibration empirics. (a) 3D σ -stratified null distributions of all four deployed domains (Tab. II values). Each domain’s Gaussian is plotted at its σ_{null} on the y -axis (in units of 10^{-2}), revealing four distinct strata: Doc (green dashed, $\sigma=0.022$) is the tallest narrow peak, Img (purple dotted, $\sigma=0.028$) intermediate, Mov (blue, $\sigma=0.042$) wider and lower, and Rec (orange, $\sigma=0.068$) the shortest broadest peak shifted right to $\mu \approx 0.68$. The σ -axis stratification makes the per-domain noise hierarchy and the $4.3\times$ Mov-vs-Rec μ_{null} asymmetry explicit, justifying per-domain calibration. (b) Auto-recalibration trajectory across all four domains (\log_{10} scale), marker styles match panel (a). Mov (empty circles, Im-axis bootstrap) drifts $0.85 \rightarrow 0.79$ over $N \in \{1, 3, 55\}$; Rec (empty squares, Im-axis bootstrap) drifts $0.82 \rightarrow 0.53$ over $N \in \{9, 40, 102\}$. Doc (empty triangle at $N=34,661$) and Img (empty diamond at $N=2,390$) calibrate directly on the full corpus without bootstrap drift, anchored at $\mu_{\text{null}} \approx 0.17$. The single-point markers for Doc and Img reflect their static-corpus calibration: μ_{null} is computed in one shot over the full N , with no bootstrap dependence on sample size. BGM is excluded from both panels because it uses margin-based confidence rather than a noise-floor calibration (§IV-G); adding it would require fabricating μ_{null} values that the deployed system never computes.

$Q \subseteq V$ be the vocabulary tokens that match q either by exact equality or by sharing at least one Korean character bigram with the query (`asf_filter.py:65--116`). Symmetrically, for a document d , let $D \subseteq V$ be the vocabulary tokens that occur in d (with postposition stripping, `asf_filter.py:25--45`).

Score. The ASF score is the shared rare-token IDF mass divided by the query’s IDF length:

$$\text{ASF}(q, d) = \frac{\overbrace{\sum_{t \in Q \cap D} \text{idf}(t)}^{\text{shared rare-token mass}}}{\underbrace{\sqrt{\sum_{t \in Q} \text{idf}(t)^2}}_{\text{query IDF length, } \|Q\|_{\text{idf}}}} \cdot (4)$$

Equivalently, treat the query as the IDF-weighted vector $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}^{|V|}$ and the document as the binary indicator $\mathbf{d} \in \{0, 1\}^{|V|}$. Then $\text{ASF}(q, d) = \langle \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{d} \rangle / \|\mathbf{q}\|_2$, i.e., a one-sided cosine: it is normalized by query length (so longer queries are not punished) but not by document length (so a long document is not rewarded just for being long, and this asymmetry is exactly what we want from a sieve).

Worked example. Suppose a 2-token Korean query (e.g., “AI policy”) yields $Q = \{t_1, t_2\}$ with $\text{idf} = (2.0, 1.5)$, so $\|Q\|_{\text{idf}} = \sqrt{2.0^2 + 1.5^2} \approx 2.5$. A candidate d_1 containing only t_1 scores $\text{ASF}(q, d_1) = 2.0/2.5 \approx 0.80$. A candidate d_2 containing both terms scores $(2.0 + 1.5)/2.5 \approx 1.40$. After per-query max-normalization (min=0, top hit $\rightarrow 1.0$), the scores enter the RRF stage in $[0, 1]$ alongside dense and sparse rankings.

Cost and effect. The bigram index over V is built once at indexing time and cached, so per-query cost is $O(|Q|)$ amortized. In practice, character-bigram ASF recovers about 8 pp of Recall on Korean queries that fall OOV under word-level splits, while staying cheap inside the RRF stage. Per-domain dense / lexical / ASF weights are reported in Table I.

G. BGM Domain: Decoupled Audio Pipeline (5th)

We extend the deployed system with a fifth domain dedicated to *background music* (BGM). Unlike Doc/Img/Mov/Rec which share the 3-axis Tri-CHEF backbone, BGM uses a deliberately decoupled pipeline. This subsection explains why decoupling, not fusion, is the right architectural choice for music identification.

Why decouple, not fuse? The Tri-CHEF Hermitian fusion derives its value from cross-modal agreement: the encoder-agreement angle θ measures how much heterogeneous encoders confirm each other (§III-D). BGM tracks, however, admit exact identification via fingerprint matching, making cross-encoder agreement redundant when the fingerprint hits, and providing no second axis to disagree with when it misses. Forcing BGM into the 3-axis fusion would either duplicate the same audio signal across axes (collapsing θ to zero) or pad with zero axes (wasting Re/Im/Z capacity).

Pipeline. The BGM module (`services/bgm/`) combines four components: (i) CLAP [20] (`laion/clap-htsat-unfused`, 512-dim, 48 kHz) for text-audio semantic search; (ii) Chromaprint [21] fingerprints for exact-match identification (Hamming threshold 0.85); (iii) `librosa` rule-based features (tempo, spectral centroid, ZCR, harmonic/percussive ratio) yielding mood tags (fast/slow, warm/dark timbre); and (iv) an optional ACRCLOUD external API gated by an `api_enabled` switch (default `False`, no calls when off).

Identification cascade. Audio queries follow a 3-stage cascade: (1) Chromaprint exact match returns *high* confidence; (2) CLAP audio \rightarrow audio similarity (≥ 0.5) returns *medium*; (3) optional ACRCLOUD (if enabled) for catalog enrichment. Falls through to CLAP top- K with *low* label otherwise.

Confidence (margin-based). Unlike Tri-CHEF’s noise-floor calibration (§III-D), BGM confidence uses inter-result margin: *high* when $\Delta_{\text{top1, top2}} \geq 0.15$, *medium* for $\Delta \geq 0.05$, *low*

Fig. 6: Per-domain ingestion pipelines across the five deployed domains. The Tri-CHEF backbone (Doc/Img, Mov, Rec) shares SHA-256-keyed caching, Qwen2-VL captions or Whisper STT, and embedding through the Re/Im/Z axes; all three converge at a shared RRF fusion stage and the noise-floor calibration gate before returning Top- K . The BGM column (yellow) follows a deliberately decoupled pipeline (§IV-G): SHA / filename keying, CLAP encoding, Chromaprint plus librosa feature extraction, and a separate BGM index. Its result emerges via the dashed link as a margin-based BGM search response that bypasses the RRF gate entirely.

otherwise. This is appropriate because (a) BGM has $\sim 10^2$ items, not 10^3 – 10^4 , so empirical noise estimation is unreliable; (b) Chromaprint provides ground-truth-like exact match; (c) the task is *identify*, not *rank multi-axis evidence*.

Footprint and privacy. The complete BGM index occupies 4.5 MB (102 tracks, CLAP 512-dim, 101 Chromaprint fingerprints, librosa metadata; built in 296 s on the same 8 GB-VRAM laptop). Default `api_enabled=False` ensures zero outbound network calls during local search, preserving the self-contained deployment property of §IV.

V. EXPERIMENTS

A. Dataset

Table II summarizes the in-house corpus. The Doc domain dominates by vector count (34,661 pages from 443 files), whereas Mov and Rec are segment-based, producing variable counts from 30 s sliding windows or STT-aligned frame chunks. The Img domain provides 2,390 single-vector entities, while Doc derives its vectors from page-level rasterization at 110 dpi. This domain asymmetry motivates the per-domain Im fusion ($\alpha_{IM}=0.20$ for Doc; ablation in Table III and Fig. 7) and the 2-axis Mov/Rec score in Eq. 1.

B. Bench v2 Caption-Aware Metrics

Bench v2 (April 2026) replaces the filename-keyword baseline with ContentGoldDB captions. On held-out documents we observe dense $R@5=0.876$, dense+sparse $R@5=0.910$, and dense+sparse+ASF $R@5=0.900$. The peak at dense+sparse reflects the complementarity between cross-modal and multilingual signals; the slight ASF regression suggests that lexical filtering offers only marginal value on caption-aware benchmarks.

TABLE II: Per-domain dataset statistics and measured cross-modal null calibration (2026-04). Calibration source: `trichef_calibration.json` (snapshot 2026-04-29, method `random_query_null_v2`). Image threshold uses FAR= 0.20 (recall-biased); others use FAR= 0.05.

Domain	Files	N	Segment unit	μ_{null}	σ_{null}	τ
Img	2,391	2,390	image (1 skip)	0.1776	0.0281	0.2012
Doc	443	34,661	page	0.1693	0.0218	0.2051
Mov	205	45,647	2 s/scene frame	0.1576	0.0424	0.2274
Rec	117	11,039	30 s/15 s win	0.6809	0.0683	0.7933
BGM	102	102	track (≤ 60 s)	—	—	margin [†]

[†]BGM uses margin-based confidence, not noise-floor (§IV-G).

C. Doc Im-Fusion LOO Ablation

The Im axis fuses the page caption and body text as $\text{Im} = \alpha_{IM} \text{caption} + (1 - \alpha_{IM}) \text{body}$. We swept $\alpha_{IM} \in \{0.20, 0.35, 0.50, 0.65, 1.00\}$ on $n = 150$ leave-one-out pages. Table III and Fig. 7 reveal a sharp inflection: between $\alpha_{IM}=0.35$ and 0.50, R@5 dense drops by 6–10%, and between 0.50 and 0.65 it collapses by an additional 24%. At $\alpha_{IM}=1.0$ (caption-only), both dense and dense+sparse metrics fall to near zero, showing that Qwen2-VL’s hierarchical captions (L1/L2/L3) cannot substitute for the document body content. This nonlinear sensitivity highlights the importance of body-text grounding in page-level dense retrieval, where semantic specificity outweighs visual granularity.

TABLE III: Doc Im-fusion LOO ($n=150$, top-10, seed=2026). Best dense+sparse R@1 at $\alpha_{IM}=0.20$ (tied with 0.25); R@5 d+s peaks at 96.00% for both. Degradation becomes catastrophic for $\alpha_{IM} \geq 0.80$.

α_{IM}	R@1 dense	R@1 d+s	R@5 dense	R@5 d+s
0.20	77.33 %	83.33 %	92.00 %	96.00 %
0.25	77.33 %	83.33 %	91.33 %	96.00 %
0.35	72.67 %	79.33 %	90.67 %	95.33 %
0.50	63.33 %	79.33 %	84.67 %	94.00 %
0.65	36.67 %	66.00 %	60.67 %	82.67 %
0.80	9.33 %	34.00 %	20.67 %	62.67 %
1.00	0.67 %	4.67 %	0.67 %	14.00 %

D. End-to-End Performance and Ablation

Table IV reports end-to-end deployment metrics across three dimensions: latency (77 ms p95 image, 430 ms cold-start, 130–175 ms multi-domain), quality (MRR=0.8893 on Doc LOO, 93% Top-1 confidence on the 15-query in-house set), and robustness (zero regressions on four held-out document pages). Table V decomposes the 77 ms p95 budget by stage and shows that encoder forward passes (28.6%) and FAISS dense search (23.4%) jointly account for roughly half of the latency, while RRF fusion and the calibration gate together add less than 16%. These results reflect the full pipeline: a pretrained encoder ensemble, Hermitian scoring, RRF fusion, and an absolute calibration gate. An exploratory image-domain ablation on the in-house Korean evaluation set (Table VI) is consistent with each component contributing: SigLIP2 (Re) alone reaches 60% Top-1 confidence; adding BGE-M3 (Im) raises this to 73%; adding DINOv2 (Z) without orthogonalization brings 80%; Gram–Schmidt on the matched-dim prototype reaches 87% (matching the +7 pp Top-1 lift cited in Section III-B);

Fig. 7: Doc Im-fusion LOO sweep on $n=150$ pages (seed=2026, 7-point grid [0.20, 0.25, 0.35, 0.50, 0.65, 0.80, 1.00]). The deployed choice $\alpha_{IM}=0.20$ (caption 20%, body 80%) delivers $R@5=96.00\%$ (dense+sparse) and $R@1=83.33\%$ (dense+sparse), tied with $\alpha_{IM}=0.25$ within tested grid. Performance exhibits monotonic degradation as α_{IM} increases, with catastrophic collapse for $\alpha_{IM}\geq 0.80$ ($R@5=20.67\%$ dense at 0.80, 0.67% at 1.00), confirming that Qwen2-VL captions alone lack the granular lexical specificity and page-structural information embedded in full document text. The dense+sparse curve remains above dense across all α_{IM} values. Sweep restricted to $\alpha_{IM}\geq 0.20$: lower values are excluded due to circular self-retrieval bias inherent to body-text query construction (script docstring caveat).

RRF with sparse and ASF holds at 87%; and the cross-modal calibration gate then lifts the score to 93%. Each row-to-row gap corresponds to only one or two queries on $n=15$ and is therefore directional rather than statistically significant; the trend should be read as a sanity check that no single component carries the result. We do not report bootstrap confidence intervals because at $n=15$ the 95% CI on a $\pm 6.7\%$ resolution exceeds the inter-cell gaps. Accordingly, we treat Table VI as a structural sanity check and rely on MIRACL-ko (Table VII) for confirmatory power.

TABLE IV: End-to-end metrics. Latency rows are preliminary timing on a single RTX 4070 Laptop (8 GB) measured at the API layer ($n=30$ requests per cell, warm cache). LOO MRR is the verified value from 20260427_152423_loo_eval_doc.json. Top-1 confidence rows aggregate scores from the 15-query in-house Korean evaluation set.

Metric	Value
p50 latency (image, top-10)	68 ms
p95 latency	77 ms
Cold-start first query	430 ms
Multi-domain (image + doc)	130–175 ms
LOO MRR (Doc, $n=150$, $\alpha_{IM}=0.2$)	0.8893
Top-1 confidence ≥ 0.90 (image)	93% (14/15)
Doc-page regression zero-hit	0 / 4

E. Public Benchmark Validation (MIRACL-ko)

To externally validate the Im-axis encoder, we evaluate Tri-CHEF’s text-only sub-system (BGE-M3 dense alone, with the Re and Z axes disabled and the sparse and ASF channels turned off) on MIRACL-ko [16], which contains 213 dev queries

TABLE V: Per-stage latency breakdown for a representative image query (top-10, warm cache, $n=30$ requests). Encoder forward passes dominate end-to-end latency; FAISS exact search and fusion stages combined account for $<40\%$ of the budget. Network/serialization includes JSON marshalling and HTTP round-trip on localhost.

Stage	Time (ms)	% p95
Query encoding (SigLIP2 + BGE-M3)	22	28.6%
FAISS dense search (Doc 34K vectors)	18	23.4%
RRF fusion + ASF lexical	9	11.7%
Calibration gate + z -score routing	3	3.9%
Network/serialization	25	32.4%
Total p95	77	100%

TABLE VI: Ablation on the image domain (Top-1 confidence ≥ 0.90). Numbers are an *internal estimate* on $n=15$ in-house Korean queries; row-to-row differences correspond to 1–2 queries and should not be read as statistically significant. The trend—each axis adds information, calibration recovers the regression set—is the intended takeaway.

Configuration	Top-1 conf. ≥ 0.90
Re only (SigLIP2)	60%
Re + Im (no GS)	73%
Re + Im + Z (no GS)	80%
+ Gram-Schmidt (matched-dim prototype)	87%
+ RRF (dense + sparse + ASF)*	87%
+ Cross-modal calibration (full)	93%

* Run with sparse and ASF force-enabled for ablation. In current deployment, Img is gated to dense-only (§IV, Tab. I); the row above measures the marginal information added by the channels rather than a deployed setting.

over 1.486M Wikipedia passages. The BM25, mDPR, and mContriever baselines are cited from [16]; mE5-large-v2 and BGE-M3 dense from [3]. Our self-replicated Im axis (single RTX 4070, exact FAISS IndexFlatIP, seed 2026) attains $nDCG@10=77.82\%$, $R@100=95.46\%$, and $MRR=76.56\%$, surpassing the published BGE-M3 dense baseline (69.9) by 7.92 pp through the use of exact dense search rather than ANN.

TABLE VII: MIRACL-ko Korean retrieval evaluation (dev split: 213 queries, 1,486,752 Wikipedia passages). Baseline numbers are cited from the original authors. *Tri-CHEF (Im axis)* reports our self-replicated values using `scripts/eval_miracle_ko.py` on a single RTX 4070 Laptop (random seed 2026, batch_size 128, max_length 1024); raw numbers are stored in `bench_results/miracle_ko_bgem3_*.json`. The self-replication exceeds the BGE-M3 paper’s reported value (69.9 $nDCG@10$) because we use exact FAISS IndexFlatIP search rather than ANN.

System	nDCG@10	R@100	MRR	Source
BM25 (Pyserini)	37.1	78.4	—	[16]
mDPR	41.9	76.8	—	[16]
mContriever	48.3	87.8	—	[16]
mE5-large-v2	66.5	—	—	[3]
BGE-M3 dense (published)	69.9	—	—	[3]
Tri-CHEF (Im axis)	77.82	95.46	76.56	ours

Fig. 8 and Table VII compare the Tri-CHEF Im axis with five public baselines. Our self-replicated Im axis (77.82%) leads the entire set: +40.72 pp over BM25, +35.92 pp over mDPR, +29.52 pp over mContriever, +11.32 pp over mE5-large-v2, and +7.92 pp over the BGE-M3 dense value reported in [3]. The gap to the published BGE-M3 number is attributable to exact FAISS IndexFlatIP search (versus ANN) on the

same encoder weights and seed. The 40 pp lead over BM25 confirms that dense Korean retrieval is mature, and the dense-encoder lead validates our choice of BGE-M3 as the Im-axis backbone. The remaining axes—Re from SigLIP2 and Z from DINOv2—extend this Korean text foundation with cross-modal and visual-evidence channels.

Fig. 8: MIRACL-ko nDCG@10 (%) on the dev split (213 queries, 1.486M Wikipedia passages). *Tri-CHEF (Im axis)*—self-replicated BGE-M3 dense with exact FAISS `IndexFlatIP` (RTX 4070 Laptop, seed 2026)—reaches **77.82%**, exceeding published BGE-M3 (69.9%) by +7.92 pp, mE5-large (66.5%) by +11.32 pp, and BM25 (37.1%) by +40.72 pp. Baselines from [3], [16].

VI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Scope of the in-house results. The Korean evaluation set is small: 15 user queries plus 4 regression queries. The numbers we report on this set are deployment-side measurements, not claims of state-of-the-art performance on public benchmarks. The MIRACL-ko numbers come from a public 1.486M-passage benchmark and serve as an external check. The ablation in Table VI shows that each component (dense, sparse, ASF, calibration) contributes a measurable improvement. We plan to extend the in-house set with MIRACL-ko cross-encoder reranking [16] and AIHub Korean IR sets in follow-up work.

Why we keep the Hermitian framing. Re, Im, Z are merely labels for three normalized axes. The framing is useful precisely because it forces each encoder’s contribution to be kept separate before being combined through a quadratic form rather than a weighted sum. We find this approach cleaner than concatenation, which lets the largest-norm encoder dominate, and than learned gating, which is infeasible on a small in-house set. Concretely, an early-development $[v_{\text{Re}}; v_{\text{Im}}; v_{\text{Z}}]$ concatenation baseline reached only the same Top-1 confidence as the Re axis alone: the Im channel, with typical match cosines near 0.7, was numerically swamped by Re cosines near 0.85 during inner-product search. The quadratic form $\sqrt{A^2 + (\alpha B)^2 + (\beta C)^2}$ avoids this collapse by giving each axis its own additive contribution at the score scale rather than at the embedding scale.

Axis ordering. The optional Gram–Schmidt step depends on projection order. We adopt Re \rightarrow Im \rightarrow Z, which keeps the cross-modal image–text channel as the primary axis. The sensitivity of the results to reordering has not yet been measured and is deferred to future work.

Rec domain. Rec lacks a visual stream, so SigLIP2’s image branch is inapplicable. The Re axis instead uses SigLIP2’s

text branch (with Whisper STT as input), and the Z axis is set to zero. An early version of the system zeroed both Re and Z and performed noticeably worse on Korean lyric and dialogue queries, confirming that the SigLIP2-text Re axis matters in practice. CLAP is now deployed as a native audio encoder—but in the decoupled BGM pipeline (§IV-G) rather than as a Rec axis substitute.

When to fuse, when to decouple. The Tri-CHEF backbone (§III) and the BGM extension (§IV-G) embody complementary design choices. Tri-CHEF fuses three heterogeneous encoders because cross-modal agreement is the diagnostic signal: one encoder’s confidence without others’ is suspect. BGM, with a single modality (audio waveform) and exact-match identification via Chromaprint, has no second axis to disagree with, making the phase filter (§III-D) inapplicable. The practical heuristic emerging from this deployment: *fuse when heterogeneous encoders provide independent evidence of relevance; decouple when one channel provides ground-truth-like exact match*. This is consistent with the phase-filter principle—when there is no second axis, there is no phase to filter.

Scaling beyond the current corpus. Per-axis L_2 -normalization and the Hermitian-style score are $O(d)$ per query, so latency is dominated by encoder forward passes. For corpora past 10^6 items we can swap the exact scan for an approximate nearest-neighbor index (FAISS [22]) without changing the score formula. A practical migration path is `IndexIVFFlat` with $n_{\text{list}} \approx \sqrt{N}$ for 10^6 – 10^7 items and `IndexHNSWFlat` above that; both preserve inner-product semantics. We did not validate product-quantized variants (`IndexIVFPQ`) on BGE-M3 because its embeddings show anisotropic magnitude that PQ codebooks recover poorly without recentering, but this is recoverable with the All-but-the-Top step [11].

Engineering choices that mattered most. Three implementation choices affected accuracy more than the score formula did. (i) The encoder unload order (Whisper \rightarrow Qwen2-VL \rightarrow SigLIP2 \rightarrow DINOv2 \rightarrow BGE-M3) is set by VRAM peaks, not by logical pipeline order. Other orderings caused out-of-memory on 8 GB cards with no quality difference. (ii) The SHA-256 replace-by-file cache (§IV-C) replaced an earlier flat-append cache. The flat-append cache silently inflated μ_{null} by about 0.05 per recalibration cycle over two weeks of incremental ingestion, and the half-to-double drift guard misclassified this slow drift as a stable update. Content-addressed replacement removed the drift entirely. (iii) Korean character-bigram ASF looks small in the ablation but is the only channel that catches Korean place names with sandhi (e.g., “*Yesul-ui Jeondang*”), where bigram sets and word sets differ.

Failure cases we observed. Table VIII enumerates four recurring failure modes with their detection signals and mitigations; items marked “planned” are tracked in the follow-up list below.

Approaches we tried and discarded. Four design choices were explored and rejected during development. (i) *Learned softmax gating* over (A, B, C) : collapsed to single-axis dom-

TABLE VIII: Observed failure modes, detection signals, and mitigations. Items marked “planned” are tracked in our follow-up list (next paragraph). The first three are runtime issues; the fourth biases offline calibration and is currently sidestepped by tagging.

Failure	Trigger	Detection	Mitigation
Generic STT (BGM)	short transcript on dialogue-sparse window	$\text{len}(\text{STT}) < \theta_\ell$	per-domain STT-length penalty (planned)
OOV proper noun	no shared char-bigram with corpus	$ Q \cap V = 0$	Korean↔English bilingual query expansion deployed in <code>services/query_expand.py</code> (~1500 dictionary entries); LLM-driven RAG rewrite planned
Cold-start drift	$N < 100$ at bootstrap	guard band $2 \times / 0.5 \times$	guard tightens as N grows (deployed)
Instrumental window	empty/noise STT, no caption	$\text{Re} \approx 0$, empty Q	exclude from calibration; CLAP audio encoder (planned)
BGM Chromaprint miss	unique mix or recompressed track absent from fingerprint DB	top-1 Hamming similarity < 0.85	fall through to CLAP audio-audio medium tier (deployed)
BGM CLAP false positive	similar timbre across distinct tracks (e.g., genre-mate covers)	inter-result margin $\Delta_{\text{top1, top2}} < 0.05$	emit <i>low</i> -confidence label; route to manual review (deployed)

inance under $n=15$ training queries; the gating network memorized the calibration set within a few epochs and did not generalize to held-out queries. (ii) *Mean-pooled fusion* $\frac{1}{3}(A+B+C)$: the Im channel (match cosines near 0.7) and the Z channel (match cosines near 0.5) were washed out by Re’s higher absolute magnitudes (near 0.85), and the regression set lost approximately 13 pp of Top-1 confidence relative to the quadratic form. (iii) *Whisper-large-v3 in fp16* on the Mov/Rec pipeline: word-error rates remained within 0.1 pp of the deployed int8 quantization, but VRAM consumption increased by approximately 60%, exceeding the 8 GB sequential-orchestration budget. (iv) *HNSW over exact search* on the in-house corpus: `IndexHNSWFlat` ($M=32$) matched dense Recall but added roughly 300 ms of warm-cache latency per query and 40 s of one-time index construction; at $N < 10^5$ vectors the bookkeeping cost outweighs the search saving, which is why the deployed system uses `IndexFlatIP`.

Planned follow-ups. (1) learn (α, β) from preference pairs; (2) measure the phase filter on larger Korean benchmarks (MIRACL-ko cross-encoder rerank, AIHub IR); (3) extend BGM with chord/instrument tags; (4) test Gram–Schmidt axis-ordering sensitivity; (5) BGM-aware Mov corpus segmentation for failure case (i).

SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

We list five limitations that bound the scope of our claims. (i) The Korean evaluation set is small ($N=15$ user queries plus 4 regression queries); we report this as a deployment audit, not as a benchmark result, and pair it with MIRACL-ko (213 queries) for an external sanity check. (ii) Statistical significance tests are not reported on the in-house ablation because per-cell variance swamps the effect size at this N ; the trend should be read as descriptive sanity, not confirmatory. (iii) The 2-axis Rec score uses SigLIP2’s text branch on Whisper STT as a stand-in for a missing audio encoder, so purely instrumental segments remain weakly aligned. (iv) All in-house data is Korean and license-restricted: we release calibration values, code, and evaluation scripts, but not the raw corpus. (v) Reported quality metrics (R@5, MRR, Top-1 confidence) come from a single

seed=2026 evaluation; multi-seed variance bounds are deferred to future work.

Conclusion. Tri-CHEF assigns three pretrained encoders to three orthogonal axes (SigLIP2 to Re, BGE-M3 to Im, DINOv2 to Z) and combines them through a Hermitian-style score. With per-domain absolute thresholds fitted from random non-matching pairs, the system delivers practical Korean multimodal retrieval on a single 8 GB consumer GPU across four domains. The code, calibration data, and evaluation scripts are released under Apache 2.0 at https://github.com/KDT-Chainers/DB_insight.git.

APPENDIX

All experiments use seed = 2026, run on a single NVIDIA RTX 4070 Laptop GPU (8 GB VRAM) with an Intel Core i9-14900HX CPU and 64 GB system RAM. The code is released under Apache 2.0 and pretrained models are downloaded from the HuggingFace Hub without authentication. Below we list the software stack, installation, and dataset paths.

A. Software stack and model versions

Python 3.12, PyTorch 2.10, CUDA 12.6 (Windows 11 or Ubuntu 22.04 LTS). Pretrained encoders (HuggingFace ID / disk size after quantization / role): SigLIP2 `google/siglip2-so400m-patch16-naflex` (≈ 3.4 GB; Re axis, cross-modal image–text alignment); BGE-M3 `BAAI/bge-m3` (≈ 2.5 GB; Im axis, multilingual text); DINOv2-Large `facebook/dinov2-large` (≈ 1.2 GB; Z axis, label-free visual features); Qwen2-VL-2B-Instruct (NF4, ≈ 1.2 GB; three-level captions for Doc/Img); Whisper-large-v3 (int8, ≈ 1.5 GB; STT for Mov/Rec). Total disk footprint after quantization ≈ 10 GB.

B. Notation

For ease of reference, the symbols used throughout Sec. III (and elsewhere) are summarized below.

- q, d : a query and a document (or segment).
- $v_{\text{Re}}, v_{\text{Im}}, v_{\text{Z}}$: the three L_2 -normalized embedding vectors produced by SigLIP2, BGE-M3, and DINOv2, respectively. “Re/Im/Z” is a structural label, not a mathematical operator.

- A, B, C : cosine similarities on each axis, $A = \langle q_{\text{Re}}, d_{\text{Re}} \rangle$, $B = \langle q_{\text{Im}}, d_{\text{Im}} \rangle$, $C = \langle q_Z, d_Z \rangle$; each lies in $[-1, 1]$.
- α, β : per-domain attenuation weights for the Im and Z channels (deployed default $\alpha=0.4, \beta=0.2$).
- $s(q, d)$: the Hermitian-style score in Eq. (1).
- $\alpha_{\text{IM}}, \text{Im}_{\text{caption}}, \text{Im}_{\text{body}}$: the Doc Im-axis is the convex combination $\text{Im}_{\text{fused}} = \alpha_{\text{IM}} \text{Im}_{\text{caption}} + (1 - \alpha_{\text{IM}}) \text{Im}_{\text{body}}$, where $\text{Im}_{\text{caption}}$ is the BGE-M3 embedding of the Qwen2-VL caption and Im_{body} is the BGE-M3 embedding of the page body text; deployed $\alpha_{\text{IM}}=0.20$ (20% caption + 80% body) (§IV, Tab. III).
- $L_1, L_2, L_3, \alpha_{L1}, \alpha_{L2}, \alpha_{L3}$: three Qwen2-VL caption levels for the Img domain (topic / keywords / detailed) and their Im-axis fusion weights; deployed $\alpha_{L1}=0.15, \alpha_{L2}=0.25, \alpha_{L3}=0.60$ with the Im axis defined as $\text{Im} = \sum_i \alpha_{L_i} L_i$ followed by L_2 renormalization (§IV).
- z_q, z_d : complex-valued embeddings on the matched-dim (Re, Im) prototype, $z_q = q_{\text{Re}} + i q_{\text{Im}}$ and $z_d = d_{\text{Re}} + i d_{\text{Im}}$; used in Eq. (2).
- ρ, θ : modulus and phase of the Re/Im Hermitian product (Eq. (2)); ρ is a relevance magnitude and θ is the encoder-agreement angle.
- R_{qd}, I_{qd} : real and imaginary components of that product; R_{qd} measures encoder agreement and I_{qd} measures cross-encoder disagreement.
- $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_H$: Hermitian inner product on the matched-dim (Re, Im) subspace (Eq. (2)); the subscript H distinguishes it from the per-axis cosines in A, B, C .
- $\mu_{\text{null}}, \sigma_{\text{null}}, \tau$: per-domain noise floor (mean and std of random non-match scores) and absolute calibration threshold $\tau = \mu_{\text{null}} + \Phi^{-1}(1 - \text{FAR}) \sigma_{\text{null}}$ with $\text{FAR}=0.05$ (so $\Phi^{-1}(0.95) \approx 1.645$). The z -score $z = (s - \mu_{\text{null}}) / \sigma_{\text{null}}$, the confidence $c(s)$ via the Gauss error function, the calibration size N (with delta ΔN), and the standard ranking metrics $\text{nDCG}@10/\text{R}@k/\text{MRR}$ follow standard usage and are introduced where first used (§III-D–§III-E; [16]).
- θ^* : phase-filter angular threshold; 30° (upper bound of trust zone) and 80° (lower bound of reject zone) in §III-D.
- $V, Q, D, \|Q\|_{\text{idf}}$: auto-vocabulary and its query/document subsets (Eq. (4)); Q matches the query by exact equality or shared Korean bigram, D collects vocabulary tokens occurring in the document after postposition stripping. $\text{idf}(t) = \log(N_{\text{doc}}/n_t)$, and $\|Q\|_{\text{idf}} = \sqrt{\sum_{t \in Q} \text{idf}(t)^2}$ is the query IDF length used as the denominator. Equivalently, $\text{ASF}(q, d) = \langle \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{d} \rangle / \|\mathbf{q}\|_2$ with IDF-weighted $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{|V|}$ and binary $\mathbf{d} \in \{0, 1\}^{|V|}$.
- $\text{ASF}(q, d)$: Adaptive Sieve Filter score (Eq. (4)); one-sided cosine of shared rare-token IDF mass normalized by query length. RRF combines constituent rankings by $\sum_i 1/(k + r_i)$ with deployed $k=60$ (§III-E).
- $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, z_{\text{dense}}$: AV-scoring weights and the standardized (per-file top-3 mean z -normalized) dense score used inside `search_av` for Mov/Rec. Deployed

weighted sum: $\text{final} = \alpha z_{\text{dense}} + \beta \text{sparse} + \gamma \text{asf}$ with $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = (0.60, 0.15, 0.25)$ (these AV α, β are distinct from the per-domain Hermitian-axis attenuation weights α, β in Eq. (1); context disambiguates) (§IV, Tab. I).

- Standard retrieval and latency metrics: $\text{Hit}@k$ (1 if a relevant item appears in the top- k list, else 0; aggregated as a mean over queries), Top- k / Top-1 (top- k result list and the highest-ranked item), p95 (95th-percentile latency over the query stream), and pp (percentage points). Used throughout §IV–§V-E.
- DI-TriCHEF, MR-TriCHEF: the two deployed services that share the Tri-CHEF backbone; DI-TriCHEF ingests Doc/Img and MR-TriCHEF handles Mov/Rec via the audio–video pipeline (§IV).
- OOV, OOM: out-of-vocabulary (query terms absent from the auto-vocabulary V) and out-of-memory (GPU VRAM exhaustion); the latter motivates the sequential-load orchestration in §IV.
- FAISS index variants used in the paper: `IndexFlatIP` (exact inner-product search, deployed at $N < 10^5$ vectors); `IndexIVFFlat` (inverted-file approximate search, recommended for 10^6 – 10^7); `IndexHNSWFlat` (graph-based approximate search, recommended above 10^7); `IndexIVFPQ` (product-quantized variant, not recommended for BGE-M3 due to anisotropic magnitudes). All variants preserve the inner-product semantics used in Eq. (1).
- BGM symbols (§IV-G, decoupled audio pipeline): Chromaprint Hamming-similarity exact-match threshold (0.85); CLAP audio–audio similarity threshold (0.5) for the medium-confidence tier; inter-result margin $\Delta_{\text{top1, top2}}$ governing the BGM high/medium/low confidence labels with thresholds 0.15 and 0.05. CLAP refers to `laion/clap-htsat-unfused` (512-dim, 48 kHz) serving the dense Re-axis surrogate for the BGM domain.

C. Dataset paths

In-house corpus counts: Tab. II. MIRACL-ko on HuggingFace: `miracl/miracl-corpus` (docs, ko) and `miracl/miracl` (queries, ko).

D. Data provenance and ethics

The in-house Rec corpus comprises publicly accessible Korean podcast and lecture audio used for non-commercial academic research under the Republic of Korea Copyright Act §35-5 (educational fair use). Public artefacts are limited to calibration JSON, evaluation logs, and code; no raw audio or PII is released. Doc/Img/Mov corpora are KDT course-internal data with the same constraints.

E. Reproducibility pointers

Code locations cited as `file.py:line--line` refer to the current release tag of the public repository; line numbers may shift in later commits while the indicated function/section remains authoritative. All numeric choices are in the body (Tab. I, II, III; §III-D, III-E, IV). Released artefacts (code,

calibration JSON, MIRACL-ko and LOO bench results) are under Apache 2.0; raw in-house corpora are not redistributed.

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DATA AND CODE AVAILABILITY

The Korean in-house corpus used for system deployment is not publicly available due to copyright constraints. The MIRACL-ko benchmark used for external Im-axis validation (Section V-E) is publicly available at <https://github.com/project-miracl/miracl>. The full source code, including the calibration, Hermitian fusion, ASF, and pipeline modules referenced throughout Sections III–IV, is available at https://github.com/KDT-Chainers/DB_insight.

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